

Oral presentation

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Effect of conservative treatments on QoL according to the SRS-22

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Background

The SRS-22 has been developed to monitor QoL in scoliosis. Only a few studies have evaluated its effects on therapies. Consequently, doubts exist on its utility in conservative treatment.

Aim

To evaluate if SRS-22 is able to detect changes in patients treated conservatively.

Study design

Pre-post and cross-sectional study.

Population

One hundred and thirty two consecutive AIS patients at their first evaluation, age 12.8 ± 2.7 , divided into 5 groups according to treatment: 30 brace for 18 hours/day, 7 for 21 h/d, 33 for 23 h/d, 48 exercises and 14 observed (controls).

Methods

All patients compiled SRS-22 before the first and at the 6 months follow-up evaluations. Statistical analysis required ANOVA and Kruskal-Wallis tests.

Results

Controls did not show changes with time, while all treated patients had increase of satisfaction with treatment. Aesthetic improvement was perceived by patients treated with exercises, while brace treated patients did show a psychological negative impact: these statistical changes were not clinically significant (0.2–0.3 points out of 5), excluding satisfaction (1.15–1.8). Between the

groups, the 23 h/d showed worst start but best results in functioning, aesthetics, pain and satisfaction.

Conclusion

SRS-22 appears to detect changes in populations, but its clinical everyday use appears less reliable.

References

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